

EMERGENCY AND HUMAN IDENTITY: A STUDY OF NAYANTARA SAHGAL'S RICH LIKE US

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Abstract

Nayantara Sahgal is a renowned author of numerous political novels, novellas, sketches, and works of journalism. She comes from a long line of wealthy Indian politicians. She has a remarkable talent for fusing fact and fiction. Sahgal's traditional faith and outlook on politics and interpersonal relationships are major elements of her literature. Looking at Sahgal's family, we can see that her parents and other family members actively participate in the fight for national freedom. Her early exposure to politics may have contributed to the skillful way she depicts political events in her literature. Her novel *Rich Like Us* contains one such instance. The real picture of India during the 1975 Emergency is provided by *Rich Like Us*. Sahgal examines how the Emergency affected the various people in this novel as well as the societal friction it caused. This research aims to analyze the novel *Rich Like Us*, its utilization of historical events, and their effects and implications on the general populace.

Keywords: Emergency, Politics, Indian History, Detention, Cultural Conflict.

One of the most well-known and prolific authors of Indian English fiction is Nayantara Sahgal. Political fiction is her main genre. She is unique in that she is the first female Indian factionalist to address political issues. According to Jasbir Jain, "She portrays India with all of its contradictions, the political situation with all of the hidden undercurrents, and such in presenting the ideal and the real working against each other, the real undermining and the ideal resisting erosion" (Dhawan. *Indian Women Novelists*. 1993. 64).

Indira Gandhi's declaration of Emergency in 1975 was a painful time for the nation. While some Indians despised it, others were unwilling to accept it. Naturally, the Emergency became the primary theme of political authors in the literary world. The declaration of emergency resulted in a number of restrictions on freedom, including censorship, arbitrary arrests, the prohibition of public gatherings, police officers wearing steel helmets lining the roads, the forcible demolition of slums, the brutally enforced vasectomies, the repression of all forms of opposition, and the concentration of power. The excesses of the Emergency are vividly depicted in Sahgal's *Rich like Us*. For this book, Nayantara Sahgal was awarded the Sinclair Prize in 1985 and the Sahitya Academy Award in 1986. The book takes place between 1932 and 1975, covering the Indian independence movement and its fallout, including Indira Gandhi's notorious declaration of a political emergency. Most critics have viewed this work as political because it daringly addresses a topic of government policy. In one instance, O.P. Mathur criticizes "*Rich like US*" only for exposing the purpose and operation of Emergency. The work, which features India as the protagonist, is praised by Jasbir Jain as a perceptive political biography. Nayantara

Sahgal contrasts the turbulent India of the Seventies with the turbulent Gandhian Age, when the desire of freedom actually blossomed, and illustrates how the Emergency weakened the nation's democracy. She discusses the transition to dynastic succession through democracy, the socio-political environment in India, its inequalities, widespread corruption, and political unrest during the 1975 Emergency. Her ominous predictions were realized with the declaration of Emergency and the ensuing restriction of rights. "Rich like Us" is primarily a work of Sahgal tradition, with a focus on the human aspects of the story that are overshadowed by political interest. According to the novelist, the situation did not suddenly strike the nation like a plague. In actuality, it is the result of a decline in moral principles that occurred among politicians, public personnel, and the general populace following independence. What happens to individuals who oppose the country's terrible emergency situation when the majority accepts it? All of this is made abundantly evident by Sahgal's various characters in the novel Rich Like Us.

Political unrest was raging while she was raised, according to her autobiography *Prison and Chocolate Cake*. The Indian liberation movement served as the setting for this political wantonness. She had witnessed her mother's and father's family actively participating in the fight for independence when she was a young child. One of the most notable of them was her maternal uncle, Pt. Jawaharlal Nehru, who went on to become India's first prime minister after independence. "With us, the growth of political awareness was a gradual and unconscious process and the most important influence on our lives," she says in *Prison and Chocolate Cake*, her first autobiography (31). It is true that throughout the early stages of their writing careers, writers are inspired and influenced by others. For them, they serve as pioneers. This pattern also applies to Nayantara Sahgal. She was born and raised in a political household during the Gandhian era, and this setting had a profound effect on both her work and outlook on life. As a fiction writer, Sahgal was influenced by a number of people, including Mahatma Gandhi and her "mamu," J.L. Nehru. Her father was the one who first instilled her political views. Her novels and other creative works are set against the backdrop of their thoughts and perceptions. Her writings incorporate Gandhian ideas on humanism, non-violence, individual liberty, morality, and other topics. Her strong belief in Gandhi is also evident in both of her autobiographies. She has expressed her feelings and sense of satisfaction at being connected to the Gandhian era in *Prison and Chocolate Cake*.

She writes:

"When Gandhi first emerged, our parents were grownups. He will never be seen by our kids. Although they will be aware of him, they will simply see him as one of the many notable figures in Indian history. However, we are actually the offspring of Gandhi's India, having been born during the period when India was undergoing a transformation from a dark to a light incarnation. Our maturation was India's transition into political maturity, a distinct form of political maturity from any previously witnessed in the globe, founded on an ideology motivated by compassion, peace, and selflessness. A pattern of distinct enchantment was woven into one's existence by the effect of these peculiar politics (Sinha 11)".

The literary world was also overtaken by the state of emergency. For many political novelists, including Nayantara Sahgal, it becomes the central issue. "Sahgal removes her disguise to make more direct than usual references to individuals and events, and she uses ambiguous language to express her disapproval of the Emergency that Mrs. Indira Gandhi imposed on the nation." according to T.N. Dhar. The English novel's interface between history and fiction. Mulk Raj Anand, O.V. Vijayan, Salman Rushdie, and Nayantara Sahgal. 150). A real-time depiction of the urgency of the emergency period is provided by Rich like Us. She has often spoken her political concerns about the socio-political environment in India, horrific incidents like the partition emergency, violence, corruption, the necessity of democracy, and other significant events.

Rich like Us is written exclusively in the Sahgal tradition. She has effectively conveyed the real picture of emergency-prone India, where power became arbitrary and an environment was created that was conducive to the growth of unscrupulous and opportunistic individuals, through the lives of several fictional characters. On the contrary, by denying them freedom and fundamental rights, the public was taken advantage of the novelist's mouthpiece is Sonali Ranade. She strongly opposes emergencies and is an idealist. Marxism is something she rejects and will never use. She makes the decision to resist emergency, which is really totalitarianism. She ultimately chooses to leave because she cannot risk her idealism to keep her job in the administration. Mahatma Gandhi once said, "Let the masses know that there are many other ways of earning a living than betraying the national interests." She shares her father's belief in this statement. While certain characters, such as Dev, Mr. Newman, and Ravi Kachru, support emergency since they may accomplish their goals there (RLU. 146). For those like Dev who wish to earn from their unlawful activities, emergency proved to be a blessing. Since both Dev and Newman focused on financial issues, they were close. While Dev, a young and successful businessman, was searching for a partner like Newman, Newman, a foreign investor, had come to India in quest of a market to establish his company. They made the decision to establish a plant for the carbonated beverage Happyola. Dev expected that all forms of protest, strikes, and disobedience would be prohibited during the emergency period.

"This emergency is exactly what we needed," "Dev stated in the conversation with Newman. The criminals are behind bars. Having an adversary was never necessary. With just one person is in charge of the nation and no one is permitted to protest in the cabinet or in Parliament, things can move forward quickly and without constant consideration of the advantages and disadvantages. Strikes are prohibited. It will be extremely beneficial to company" (RLU. 2).

The Ministry of Industry's confirmation of the cooperative agreement took no more than ten minutes. Along with this money, the project plan was given to the minister for prompt approval. "We need contact in political circles," Dev repeatedly stated (RLU. 13). Dev and other opportunists will do everything in their power to ensure that they benefit from the deal so that they can become well-known among new business owners and be able to

abandon his sick father's clothing company. The foundation stone will be laid in two months, which will mark the beginning of Dev's takeoff.

The bureaucrats believed they had absolute power during the emergency period, and politicians and officers in high-ranking administrative positions were corrupted and cooperating to get by. Lawyers, teachers, and editors were among the various classes that supported the emergency and believed that this tyranny was normal. It was during a dinner party at Sonali's place that we learned about them. "This dictatorship was not man-made; it was a marvel of nature." "Of course it was...What was wrong with a child replacing his mother in this republic? And what mother in the world wouldn't sacrifice everything for her son? In support of emergency implementers, the top editor of a newspaper said, "Especially when he's shown such organizational talent" (RLU. 100). According to the attorney, the constitution should be changed to give Madam (P.M.) the authority she needs to combat the nation's oppressive institutions. Even the civil services, which once served as a "steel frame" for protection, are now being used to support the emergency. Over the past few years, the line between politics and the military has gotten so hazy that it has virtually vanished. Politicians were interfering in management, and the two factions were irreparably divided. Politics and civil services were no longer mutually exclusive.

The true face of emergency and its proponents is revealed through Sonali's narration, wit, and sardonic emotions. The ICS Ravi Kachru, who is observed hovering around the "political bosses", is used by her as an example. He was "indispensable here, there, and everywhere, the right hand and left leg of the Prime Minister and her household" (RLU. 23). He had learned a lot about the political game. When she rejected Happyola's plan, deeming it irrelevant for the nation, Ravi Kachru took her place. She was completely unaware that the Prime Minister's younger son would be using the Happyola factory to covertly store the auto parts needed to make automobiles. She eventually had to pay a high price for it, being demoted and sent back to her home state, "where there was no vacancy at my level, as I already knew and the Union government definitely knew. "I had been demoted, disciplined, and humiliated in addition to being abruptly relocated, and I had no idea why" (RLU. 27).

The state of emergency has given the prime minister the opportunity to change the constitution in order to exercise her power indiscriminately. Birds of the same feather flock together, so the saying goes. In an emergency, persons with similar temperaments were brought closer to one another. "In order to strengthen the Prime Minister's authority, attorneys, academics, and business forums should provide significant public support for constitutional reform" (RLU, 84). Rallies were held in support of the emergency, and delegations of educators, attorneys, schoolchildren, members of the general public, and others visited the prime minister to congratulate her on her emergency declaration and to sing songs of praise. They patiently await their opportunity to speak with the prime minister. The novelist humorously depicted this circumstance as follows:

"And then the Emergency was so popular." It was evident from the daily delegations of educators, attorneys, students, and others who came to congratulate the Prime Minister on the announcement. At the gate, they were halted. While they waited, she was certain

that they, like her, had nothing noteworthy on their minds. They did, however, share the mystical glow of pilgrims who had travelled far and dangerously to give pilgrim kisses to the big toe that was already worn out, or people doing the proper patriotic thing” (RLU. 87).

On the other end, defenceless individuals were subjected to illogical torment. Nishi's father, a shopkeeper named Kishori Lal, tells his tale of injustice. A police officer completely destroyed his store because he had not set up his space in accordance with the new regulations. For instance, whether or not he has a price tag on each item in his store. Nishi wanted him to go to the PM's house with his group of businessmen to congratulate her, but she demanded that he adhere to the emergency regulations. For what he should congratulate, resentful Kishori Lal remarked, "For slapping a whole lot of people into jail? For failing to indicate prices on things, they almost put me in jail. They don't require a valid explanation. Just head straight to jail. You should have your brain checked if that is something to be congratulated on. (RLU, 90). Enchanted by the emergency, Nishi was mistreating her parents. She once chastised them for failing to attend the Happyola factory's foundation stone ceremony. Dev, their son-in-law, requested that K.L. start an agency for Madam's (P.M.) son's vehicle. "Being an agent for P.M.'s son's car is more dignified" (RLU. 92) than selling bathroom supplies.

Ravi recently concentrated on making the Twenty Point Program, which was established during emergencies, more widely known. He has arranged a gathering of ladies for this reason, allowing them to take part and make use of their abilities in promoting emergency measures such as a beauty program or a vasectomy campaign. Another emergency advocate, Leila, recommended that their top concern should be birth control. Everyone in the meeting praised her formal thoughts and the trustworthy facts she presented. "It is quite obvious what our first goal should be". "That's what I was saying before you came. Birth control. We must learn from the government. I've heard from reputable authorities that professors who are unable to attest to having five persons sterilized will be fired. Naturally, they must first sterilize themselves. There is no nonsense about it; we need to develop a program like that for domestic employees (RLU. 94)".

One of the toughest aspects of the emergency was vasectomy. Leila's conversation makes clear how poorly treated the impoverished servants were. "I've again threatened to fire my ayah if she has second child, but she keeps acting up. It's her fourth. It is a bad dream, I tell you. "Tie her tubes" (RLU, 93).

It was determined to vasectomise Hindus first after everything fell into place. Despite being a secular state, Muslims and Christians were excluded from this program in order to avoid any form of criticism. "It's a secular state, "Leila stated. Let's start with the Hindus, though. To demonstrate that we mean business, let's simply get started. We should schedule one of those vans, set up a vasectomy centre, and transport all of our servants there on the same day. It has to do with organization and management" (RLU. 95).

Everyone involved in this vasectomy campaign sent their servants to the centers right away, viewing it as their religious obligation. It was blatantly inappropriate for Nishi to drag

an elderly servant named Kumar to the vasectomy facility. In between, an agitated Rose obstructed, saying, "This man is your father's age." "Would you take your dad to a camp for vasectomy? (RLU, 97)". Her slaves were bundled into the van, and Rose could feel their terror. Nishi was searching for another victim to make up for the loss caused by Kumar, but Ross's efforts kept Kumar safe. Her gaze suddenly landed on the beggar, who was unable to resist due to his crippling condition and handles; fortunately, he succeeded to get free.

There was complete confusion throughout the emergency period. Politicians, administrators, bureaucrats, and the general public couldn't understand it. They simply followed the current. According to RLU (p. 104), some believed that a millennium had arrived with an emergency "headed by a mother Tsar whose ignorant little peasants were quite happy with Mother's blessings." She was in a reflective mood after the dinner party at Sonali's house. She concluded that the state of emergency and PM were not the only factors that had caused confusion; confused individuals who heedlessly supported evacuations were also to blame.

Sonali returned to the time when the emergency was declared. She was thinking back to J.P.'s remarks from the evening before the emergency was declared. He was apprehended similarly to Socrates. She couldn't understand the chaos and lawlessness. To preserve her dignity, she will not surrender to such a dictatorship but will instead pursue the road of truth (Satyagraha). The worsening of the situation truly irritated her. Kishori Lal was taken into custody but not charged. The reason government orders cannot be disregarded is because three police officers showed up, turned his store upside down, and imprisoned him.

K.L. discovers in prison that while influential people were swiftly and honourably freed, some inmates—such as an American-educated boy—who were detained on fictitious or fabricated grounds—such as merely belonging to the Marxist Party—remain there indefinitely. K.L. is forced to reflect while incarcerated. According to the Bhagvad Gita, the Lord spoke. Nishi was told by her mother about K.L.'s detention and the repercussions for defying the emergency. The gas cylinder took many days to arrive, their phone was unplugged, and the electricity was turned off. To purchase kerosene oil for cooking, she must wait in a never-ending line. In these situations, even their neighbors showed them no compassion by forbidding them from using their phones out of concern for impending danger.

Throughout *Rich like Us*, the author skilfully blends social and political themes. Sonali and Rose are meant to be the novelist's spokespersons. Both have talked about how the state of emergency changed their lives. Those who support it are severely hurt by such remarks. "The omniscient author's stance is changed by the participant-narrator point of view, which is a very effective narrative device chosen by Nayantara Sahgal for the authentic portrayal of the current socio-political chaos, according to Vijayasree" (Dhawan. *Indian Women Novelists. Set II, Vol. 5, 1993: 26*). Sahgal's characters in the book represent the struggles and hardships of everyday people. The writer has expertly integrated the emergency's setting, horrors, and aftermath. Many tyrants had been born

out of the emergency, and many victims had fallen into their grips. The Ram-Rose family, which housed both victims and monarchs, was the ideal example of it. The various aspects of emergencies that are most appropriate for both Indian and Western traditions have been accurately reflected in this family. A successful attempt has been made to illustrate the characters' displeasure amid emergency situations by showing their personal difficulties.

Ram was a hardworking businessman with his own set of conventional business ethics, as can be shown by closely examining his family. He has amassed a substantial fortune for his spouses, Mona and Rose. Dev, his only son, was often at odds with him. He had no desire to work for his father's company. In addition to giving him security and bullying power, emergency has given him the chance to establish himself as a business. He unintentionally forged his father's signature to withdraw a sizable sum of money from his account in his tangle of success and avarice. Sonali subsequently told Rose about all of this. Even though everything belonged to Rose's husband, Dev and his wife Nishi were so bitter toward her that they wouldn't give her any money she requested to cover her daily expenses. Human fates have been altered by emergency.

Sahgal pays great attention to the lives of her female characters, who experience a number of highs and lows both personally and within their social circles. Rose portrays the difficulties of acculturation to a completely different culture, tradition, and nation; Mona represents injustice and mistreatment; and the novel also includes social ills like early marriages and Sati tradition to emphasize certain points. Rose's voyage has been depicted as alternating between East and West cultures. When she first met Ram in London, their characteristics captivated each other. Rose discovered a stable future and a wealthy Indian businessman in Ram. She loves Ram to become his second spouse after leaving her parents. When she first arrived in India, she was confronted with the harsh realities of her surroundings. The two cultures were very different from one another. Adjustment was clearly a problem. Ram's traditional family was also unable to accept an English bride. Ram's first wife, Mona, could not stand her and gets furious every time she sees Rose. Since she took his mother's place, Dev dislikes her. Later on, she fully adopts the Indian way of life. She makes friends with the family members. Prior to her passing, Mona entrusted Rose with the duty of Dev's marriage. As she lay dying, Mona begged, "Our daughter-in-law." After saying, "You will take care of her, won't you, Rose-ji" (RLU. 210), she passed out, allowing Rose to take over her position and duties. Rose never wanted to take Mona's place at the expense of Mona's life. Rose was the one who saved her when Mona set her on fire. "It's odd how within those walls they had adventured over hills and woods into another pasture, into friendship, and one fine morning, into love," recalls Rose, referring to the English poet Ram's poem "A way we both shall understand" (RLU. 211).

Because of her intense love, respect, and regard for Rose, Sonali felt compelled to investigate all of the options available to her for visiting the well late at night. She finds it incomprehensible that someone as vibrant as Rose should end her life after drinking too much. "When Rose had had a drink or two, it was very evident how steady she was on

her feet, talking care to put her feet heavily on the ground in a slow, measured way" (RLU. 285). Other than this, she never chooses the stony route that leads from the youth camp or takes a walk after supper. Sonali chooses to ask the beggar for further information. When Rose was intoxicated, she was making caustic comments about wrongdoers, such as Dev and his foolish group of pals and business acquaintances. It was difficult to imagine the level of desperation that must be driving her to the well. "When Rose had had a drink or two, it was very evident how steady she was on her feet, talking care to put her feet heavily on the ground in a slow, measured way" (RLU. 285). Other than this, she never chooses the stony route that leads from the youth camp or takes a walk after supper. Sonali chooses to ask the beggar for further information. When Rose was intoxicated, she was making caustic comments about wrongdoers, such as Dev and his foolish group of pals and business acquaintances. It was difficult to imagine the level of desperation that must be driving her to the well.

Here, Sonali recalls the murder of her great-grandmother, who was forcibly placed on the altar of sati by her family, who subsequently dubbed it "sacrifice." According to Sahgal's interpretation, these episodes highlight the blatant cruelty and animality inflicted upon women. Sonali, who was devastated, gathered Rose's possessions and planned to visit the beggar to learn the reason for Rose's unexpected passing. Even yet, she was reminded by an inner voice that "Rose's killers would never be brought to justice. "They would die patriotic citizens and lead comfortable lives" (RLU. 286). In an ancient tomb close to the well, Sonali encountered the beggar "curved foetus like against it," concealed behind the moss-covered wall (RLU. 290). He represents the terrible face of emergency and is one of the most tragic and miserable victims. He came out upon seeing Sonali. His face showed signs of panic and fear as he was dependent on other people's kindness. When Rose stated, "A man should at least be able to wipe away his own tears," she was being extremely reasonable" (RLU. 290). Rose has experienced the agony of having a disability. She had compassion for the beggar. When she saw the handless beggar, her heart broke. In order for him to make a living, she and Sonali have set up artificial hands for him. She would prefer that you be safe (RLU. 289). The beggar witnessed the murder of the same Rose.

The beggar told the heartbreaking tale of the most heinous incident. The beggar told Sonali, in tears, that two toughs from the youth camp had choked Rose to death. After killing her, she was thrown into the well. "It was too late...to ameliorate a fearsome catastrophe, but not too late for me to wonder when the tale of peaceful change I had been serving from behind my desk had become a tale of another compassionate, with citizens broken on the wheel for remembering their rights," Sonali realizes after reading the melancholic story of Rose and the beggar" (RLU. 291).

The murder of Rose, the beggar's severed hands, and Sonali's appalling situation were all caused by the evildoings of those in positions of authority. "It is their raj around here, after all" (RLU. 290). In the beggar's village, his hands were severed simply for claiming his portion of the land, as if it were the landlord's raj. "Power had changed hands, but what else had changed where he lived?" is how Sonali feels about this circumstance. This

was the emergency, if there had ever been one (RLU. 292). The emergency affected all three of them, who were attentive of one another, in one way or another. Since Sonali had determined that "as against justice for the dead which would never be done, there was no need to imperil the employment and security of the living, "she advised the beggar not to speak a word about what he saw near the well that night when Rose was strangled and thrown into it" (RLU. 289).

Sonali's consciousness is used to depict Rich Like Us. Although she has always promoted idealism, her tower of principles trembles like sand during an emergency. A person like Sonali's tenacity and resolve have always enabled her to fend against evil powers and never give in. She has cultivated her father's principles and ideals, who has always encouraged her to be an opponent and a fighter in the strange world of politics. She realized that she had been nourished on "the orgy of idealism" for so long until she was demoted and stripped of her job" (RLU. 31). We are taught to accept this kind of idealism rather than to avoid it. We have adopted brutality and injustice as a result of this. She soon realizes, however, that she would never continue her work "in the crumbling lack of professionalism that bowed and scraped to a fictitious emergency" (RLU. 32) after waking up from her fantasy world nightmares while still blindfolded.

It is important to note that, despite the glaring ugliness of the world, emergency served to highlight the richness of the people' personalities and the comprehensiveness of sensitive characters like Sonali, Rose, and the beggar. They suffered greatly as a result of the harsh lash of urgency. They display a bright and wonderful aspect of their personalities in place of all these tortures, a true asset that is impervious to emergencies and other calamities. These characters are as rich in Indian mythology as our history and traditions. Sonali and the impoverished beggar forgive and forget everything, and they proceed with renewed fervour and zeal. Despite their brilliance and enlightened independence, even the most vile person appears to be impoverished and beggarly.

Sahgal illustrates how, amid the internal situation, politicians, bureaucrats, and other opportunists lost their morals and ethics. Individuals like Dev went above the bounds of flattery and eventually became Cabinet Ministers. Ravi Kachru was transferred after falling from Madam's grace. Lastly, the novel illustrates how the entire political structure has undergone significant change, with both the people and the values deteriorating. According to Jasbir Jain, "Rich Like Us challenges all known solutions rather than providing any answers to humanity's problems." The complexity of reality is the ultimate theme of Rich Like Us" (The Emperor's New Clothes: The Emergency and Sahgal's Rich Like Us, p. 34). Emergency doesn't display its conclusion, but characters like Sonali give the book a hopeful conclusion. She makes the decision to struggle against the cruelty of the modern world, just as her father did when he disobeyed the sati tradition. According to Mini Nanda, "the novel's ending offers hope and a certain confidence and affirmation." The text and environment of women's writing.

Given the dreary and oppressive atmosphere that pervaded the entire book, Rich Like Us also explores the innermost thoughts of a few delicate characters who propagate the idea of becoming "Rich" like them. Humanistic elements are prevalent in Sahgal's books, and

Rich Like Us appears to be no exception. As Jasbir Jain correctly notes in *The New Indian Novel in English*, Sahgal thoroughly examines and interprets a variety of facets of political life through her active participation in politics. “The narrative turns into a concern for the quality of life as she highlights the humanistic principles she supports. Her interest in politics is only a component of her humanistic concerns since every investigation she makes into political life reveals her more recent and deeper insight into the human psyche” (Jain. 141).

The largest democracy in the world was functioning as a dictatorship during the Emergency. Since the story begins in the aftermath of the emergency, it examines and challenges historical political relationships and value systems by going back more than 150 years. For various people, emergency meant different things. Some saw it as power, opportunity, and plenty. For the average men, it was just exploitation and a denial of even the most fundamental freedom, but for others, it was a time for heroism. Sonali is demoted to a lower position, and Ravi Kachru becomes the Joint Secretary in her place. While Kachru consistently stays on the right side of power by avoiding controversies and taking the proper path, she is demoted, punished, and humiliated. In order to play a crucial part in Emergency's succession, he transforms himself into a puppet.

"Kachru would undoubtedly overcome any charade with his level of fitness. He was astounded by the realities". (RLU 26) Despite being a small character in the book, the beggar serves as a potent metaphor for the consequences of the brutal Emergency. The crippled beggar is arguably the most significant symbol in the novel, according to Makarand Paranjape. The Indian masses, which have been beaten and handicapped by the ruling class, are symbolized by the beggar. “They are defenceless and mute. Victims of unending injustice and persecution” (RLU 14)

Sahgal's work *Rich like US* is filled with physical accounts of the devastation and carnage caused by the past. "Bodies are capable of remembering histories, even when we forget them," writes Sara Ahmad. Broken, crippled corpses serve as a metaphor for the state's brutal tactics against the defenseless populace in Sahgal's book. Sahgal's book effectively captures the effects of torture on a number of characters during an emergency. The novel provides a clear-eyed picture of the violence and events of Emergency.

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